

Precision grazing management- understanding farmer uptake of grazing software

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Abstract

Increased precision in grazing management decisions requires regular pasture measurement and effective use of the data for enhanced decision-making. Technology adoption theory can help to provide insights on the incentives and barriers to uptake and on-farm adaptation of precision farming tools. In this study, we used an inductive workshop process with experts in grazing management software design and marketing to explore software adoption by farmers. Important factors included alignment of data for monitoring key performance indicators, using data for benchmarking and reporting, enabling farm team communication. Discontinued use by farmers was seen to be influenced by; technology features being misaligned with farmer practice, users not having the skills required to interpret data, practice change inertia, and farmers lacking the time to invest in learning. Future research aimed at understanding those farmers who apply 'best practice' in respect to grazing management, either with or without the use of precision farming tools, would guide better product development.

Background

There are opportunities to optimise pasture grown and pasture harvested in New Zealand dairy farming through use of precision grazing approaches. These opportunities include: regular and objective pasture measurement, use of grazing management software, and use of mobile technologies to link the farm team into the grazing process. However, use of pasture measuring tools and grazing management software remains limited on New Zealand dairy farms (King et al. 2010, Eastwood et al. 2017a).

Factors influencing adoption of agricultural technologies have been widely studied for decades, dating back to seminal studies such as Rogers (1962). These early lessons have been adapted and enhanced in recent studies, for example the adoption of renewable energy innovation systems (Meijer et al., 2007), adoption of decision support tools (Rose et al. 2016), and uptake of new agricultural practices (Kuehne et al. 2017). The important factors identified in these studies are summarised in Table 1. Kuehne et al. (2017) summarised adoption factors into a predictive quantitative model. The range in the factors identified in these studies (and in the multitude of other studies) highlight that uptake of new technologies or practices can be influenced by some common factors: technology performance, ease of use, relative advantage, and trialability. However, there will also be technology-specific factors that influence uptake – such as the uncertainty around the innovation, roles of farmer networks (Eastwood et al. 2012), and farm business characteristics.

To enable the design of effective grazing software tools for farmers, a better understanding of the factors that drive uptake is required. The aim of this current paper was to identify the factors that influence the uptake of grazing management software for dairy farming. The study was part of a larger project on precision grazing as outlined in (Eastwood et al. 2017a, Eastwood et al. 2016a).

Table 1. Summary of studies identifying factors influencing adoption of agricultural technologies

Rogers (1962)	Meijer et al. (2007)	Kuehne et al. (2017)	Rose et al. (2016)
Relative advantage	Technological uncertainty	Relative Advantage for the Population: profit, environmental and risk orientation; enterprise scale; management horizon; short term constraints. Learnability Characteristics of the Innovation: Trialable; Innovation complexity; Observability. Learnability of Population: Advisory support; Group involvement; Relevant existing skills & knowledge; Innovation awareness. Relative Advantage of the Innovation: Relative upfront cost of innovation; Reversibility of innovation; Profit benefit in years that it is used; Future profit benefit; Time until any future profit benefits are likely to be realised; Environmental costs & benefits; Time to environmental benefit; Risk exposure; Ease and convenience.	Performance
Observability	Resource uncertainty		Ease of use
Trialability	Competitive uncertainty		Peer recommendation
Compatibility	Supplier uncertainty		Trust
Reinvention	Consumer uncertainty		Cost
Complexity	Political uncertainty	Habit	Relevance to user
			Farmer-adviser compatibility
			Age
			Scale of business
			Farming type
			IT education
			Facilitating conditions
			Compliance
			Level of marketing

Methods

Sixteen commercial and research providers of grazing management software attended a one-day workshop in Hamilton, New Zealand. The workshop examined the motivating or demotivating factors for farmers using, or not using, grazing management software. An inductive workshop process was used where a basic matrix framework (factors motivating current users, demotivating current users, motivating non-users, and demotivating non-users) was used to elicit responses from attendees. Responses were captured on via participant and researcher notes, then mind-mapped using Decision Explorer™ software and analysed for the main themes. A summary of the outcomes was also provided to participants for comment after the workshop.

Results

Workshop participants identified a wide range of factors motivating or demotivating users, and non-users, of grazing management software. The main *stimulating* and *inhibiting* factors have been categorised in Figure 1. Important stimulating factors included:

- *Good technology features* that made it easy for farmers to use pasture data, and integrate it with other data sources. Features included ease of use and learnability.
- *External compliance and proof of practice* influences, such as collecting data for compliance and for milk processors, agri-finance organisations, and corporate governance. Reporting on key performance indicators to farm investors is becoming increasingly important, as is data collection for compliance software such as Overseer™.
- Ability to *trial the software* on their own farm, without wasting a farmer's time. Farmers should be able to easily cease use and export data to a standard format if required.
- *A proactive management philosophy* of the farmer or farm owner – for example, needing data to make proactive decisions, striving for excellence, competition with other farmers (benchmarking), identifying feed surpluses early, simplifying tasks to get more time away from the farm, and making the most of the pasture resource. Also, farmers who didn't trust intuition and were comfortable with structured and organised information on pasture performance might be more comfortable with the software.
- The role of software as a *communication and learning tool for the farm team*, for example providing feedback to staff on the consequences of grazing decisions. Good software can be used to communicate plans to staff, manage multiple staff, enable jobs to be tracked and to facilitate learning for new staff. Features such as smartphone apps have been shown to be important for farmers in this role (Eastwood et al., 2017a).

- Importantly, there needed to be a *belief that use of the software would make a positive difference* to the farming operation. Underlying this was the need to see (and understand) the value proposition, and to see how using the data and software would lead to capture of these benefits. This belief was also seen to be underpinned by an attitude toward technology, and experience of a tangible (or emotional) reward from using software.

Figure 1. Summary of the factors inhibiting and stimulating use of grazing software and tools

Non-adoption, or dis-adoption, by farmers was seen to be influenced by inhibiting factors including:

- Mismatch of technology design with farmer practice.* For example, workshop participants said that farmers could be deterred by software that was too complex to be usable, or too simple to be meaningful. Farmers often also feel time spent at a computer is not part of 'real farming' and that they know their farm well and therefore 'don't need to be told what to do by a computer'. Participants identified the range of dairy farming 'segments' in New Zealand and noted that farmers often felt that current tools were not flexible enough to match their specific needs (for example operating with many staff, or across multiple farms, or with a range of feed inputs).
- Flaws or misunderstandings of technology performance* can be an inhibitor to uptake. According to workshop participants these included: functionality across operating systems (Windows PC, Apple OS), not linking with other management tools, and the time requirement to set up the farm characteristics (paddocks, herd information). Other issues identified were companies stopped developing a product further, and/or frustration around installing upgrades. One bad experience could be an inhibitor to a farmer trying software in the future.
- Lack of a value proposition (or lack of awareness of the value)* was seen as a significant inhibitor. While scientists and technology developers believed there was a value proposition in investing time and money in more objective decision-making, farmers often didn't perceive a sufficient return on their investment. This was underpinned by factors such as confusion about which software option was best for their farm, or a general lack of awareness about the grazing software available or an awareness of the available features.
- Adaptation of practice* is another potential inhibitor for farmers. Participants raised several examples, including a reluctance to enhance skills needed to use information technology, not trusting the data collected, and farmers feeling that pasture measurement took too long and/or wasn't a priority.

- *Tools solving a problem farmers did not recognise* (e.g. a problem they don't think they have). Participants felt that many farmers still prefer to trust their own judgement and use a visual non-measured estimate of pasture mass. Participants felt farmers often didn't understand that managing pasture quality was more important than short-term quantity, and that 'just in time' management processes were needed to manage pasture effectively. There were also comments that too many farmers believe they are doing better than average '80% of farmers think they are in the top 20%' so this infers a belief that there isn't room for improvement.
- *A lack of knowledge on how to make best use of the data* was linked to the perception of a value proposition. If farmers were not comfortable with understanding the key performance indicators to look for in their operation, then it could be difficult to know how to best apply grazing software. Participants felt some farmers lacked confidence in using the tools, and therefore preferred to stay with their current, more intuitive methods. The potential role of farm consultants was mentioned, with some participants feeling that there was a disincentive for consultants to help farmers use software tools as it could replace their core business.

Discussion

A better understanding of approaches toward grazing management will help to guide design and marketing of precision grazing tools. The findings from this study indicates that there are a range of possible inhibiting and stimulating factors influencing the adoption of decision support software. While software developers cannot hope to design products that are 'all things to all people', it was obvious from this study that software needs to be flexible enough to be relevant to a range of farmer perspectives and farm business structures. This aligns with findings from a study of grazing management among New Zealand dairy farmers (Eastwood et al. 2017a). A different value proposition may be required for different farmer segments, for example the functionality needed by large multi-farm or corporate operations may be very different from that needed by individual owner-operators.

Understanding the general psychology around the use of precision farming tools was also seen as important by workshop attendees. Participants noted that often the reasons for adoption or non-adoption were 'hidden' and that this was manifested in many farmers always finding reasons not to use precision tools. Therefore, there was a need to better understand the different motivators for farmers and their key influences. Including farmers, and other stakeholders such as farm consultants, in the design process is an important method of incorporating these 'hidden' psychological factors and determining what role rural professionals have in the adoption process (Douthwaite et al. 2001).

Among the inhibiting factors there was little discussion of the cost of grazing software. This reflects the view from participants (commercial and research providers of grazing management software) that the price of software (ranging from NZD\$100-\$1000 p.a.) represented a minimal cost for farmers. In other studies on the use of agricultural decision support software, cost has been shown to be important for farmers when the value proposition, or return on investment, is not clear (Rose et al., 2016). Where there are so many potential inhibiting factors, including the need for farmer practice change from experienced-based decision making to data-driven decision making, even a small cost may prove a barrier to use.

Additionally, there will be other costs for farmers (perceived and real) including the time taken to set up software, learn to use, and engage staff. The importance of peer influence (farmer to farmer knowledge exchange), highlighted as important in other studies (Rose et al. 2016; Kilpatrick & Johns 2003), was not identified as a major inhibiting or stimulating factor. This may be because the participants were commercial technology and research providers and therefore not cognisant of all factors important to farmers. This should be considered when interpreting the findings of this study.

In the workshop, there was also a discussion on knowledge building for the use of precision tools in general and the roles for different organisations in the New Zealand dairy farming context. These included: the role of technology developers in designing and marketing tools that fitted the adoption factors (for example Figure 1); the role of universities and primary industry training organisations in lifting understanding and skills in precision approaches, and conducting social research into adoption psychology; industry organisation roles (e.g. DairyNZ, Federated Farmers, milk processors) in elucidating the value proposition for precision technologies and building agreement and awareness of key performance indicators for pasture management; roles of rural professionals (e.g. farm consultants, banks, fertiliser companies) in incorporating data and cloud-based software systems in their business models; and roles of farmers/farming companies to train their staff and build modern

data-driven business structures. These roles have also been discussed in other studies, for example the roles of industry organisations and technology developers were outlined in studies of precision dairy innovation systems in New Zealand (Eastwood et al. 2016b) and Australia (Eastwood et al. 2017b). Also, the potential for industry organisations to lead precision grazing uptake was highlighted where the combination of benchmarking within the farmer community, training, social media, and discussion groups has been shown to be effective stimulating factors for uptake of grazing software in Ireland (Hanrahan et al., 2017).

Conclusion

This study highlighted several factors that inhibit or stimulate the use of grazing software. These factors will be useful for informing design of precision livestock farming technologies, and providing a guide to aspects needing a co-development approach. Future research should focus on clarifying the critical farmer decisions made during the seasonal grazing management process. This can then be used to match the information inputs required at each decision point to determine the most relevant decision tools.

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